

LEVEL OF PEER PRESSURE INFLUENCE AND MENTAL WELL-BEING AMONG THE GRADE ELEVEN STUDENTS

Divine Grace C. Obispo, Blessie Ella Marie N. Jimenea, Krisha Faye L. Orbigoso, Angelie A. Orbigoso, and Jose Leonardo L. Degillo, PhD, RGC, LPT, RPsy, MAT

*College of Arts and Sciences, Kabankalan Catholic College, Inc.,
Kabankalan City, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the level of peer pressure influence and mental well-being among the grade eleven students of Kabankalan Catholic College, Inc. during the school year 2023-2024. It employed a method of correlational study design using two (2) quantitative questionnaires: the Perceived Peer Pressure Scale and The Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-Being Scale. The findings demonstrated that the level of peer pressure influence among the participants as a whole is moderate. It signifies that students experience peer pressure and influence in a multitude of ways. When grouped according to sex and strands, the findings indicated that women are more likely than men to encounter peer pressure. Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) showed the highest mean compared to the other academic strands. In terms of mental well-being, men scored higher than women. Similarly, it appears that women were more likely than men to experience psychological difficulties. STEM students had the highest mental well-being compared to the three academic strands. The results of the study indicated a strong association between peer pressure and mental well-being. Hence, the study rejects the null hypothesis, indicating that there is no significant difference between the level of peer pressure influence and mental well-being among the grade eleven students of Kabankalan Catholic College, Inc. The findings call for continuous development and the provision of comprehensive programs, seminars, and activities that increase understanding of peer pressure influence and the necessary actions to mitigate mental struggles with the goal of promoting students' mental well-being.

Keywords: *Peer Pressure Influence, Mental Well-being, Grade Eleven Students, Academic Strands, Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), Sciences, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM), Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM), Technical Vocational and Livelihood (TVL), and Sex.*

INTRODUCTION

Everyday interactions with individuals have a substantial impact on one another, and peer pressure is a social dynamic that individuals have encountered. In a developmental transition, students are especially susceptible to impacts coming from their social environment. Their peer group and faculties may support or jeopardize their health and well-being and face challenges relating to their developmental and behavioral needs. Peer pressure described as one variable that affects teenage behavior. Both positive and negative results are possible from it (Tripathy, 2018). Teenagers, therefore, frequently experience intense emotional swings that can cause observable mood extremes, impact their academic performance, undermine their self-worth, deter them from socializing with friends and peers, or even cause behavioral changes and engagement in risky activities. As a result, the presence of peer pressure is a possible predictor for increased stress levels, anxiety, and sleep issues in the youth (Anniko et al., 2018).

During the period of adolescence, teenagers go through various changes. In this phase, peer pressure and a need to fit in significantly influence adolescents' emotional well-being and psychological development. Peers play a bigger role and can be a great source of social support. The need to fit in and conform to social norms often leads individuals to make choices and engage in behaviors that may be detrimental to their well-being (Aneja, 2023).

Typically, most conventional research only limits the notion of exploration of how pressure affects the mental well-being of an adult rather than focusing in the level of adolescence. A knowledge gap that stops individual from fully understanding how to deal with friend and peer pressure as they connect to and influence one's mental well-being. The idea of peer pressure influences is being disregarded, and the majority of reviews exclusively focus on academic pressure, leaving out the influence and pressure of peers. The considerable significance of peer influence on behavioral choices is obviously complex and requires further research in the context of offering treatments and assessing adolescents' mental health.

In light of the foregoing, this study aimed to ascertain the level of peer pressure influence and mental well-being among grade eleven students at Kabankalan Catholic College, Inc. Understanding this association will provide students with important new perspectives on how peer pressure affects mental health and the abstract nature of peer pressure. The present investigation aimed to bridge the existing knowledge gaps and enhance the understanding of this particular construct.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of peer pressure influence of the participants as a whole and in each of the following subscales:
 - 1.1 Yielding to Peer Pressure
 - 1.2 Resistance to Peer Pressure
 - 1.3 Peer Encouragement
2. What is the level of mental well-being of the participants in terms of sex and academic strands.
 - 2.1 Sex
 - 2.2 Academic Strands
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of peer pressure influence when grouped according to sex and academic strands?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of mental well-being of the participants when grouped according to sex and academic strands?
5. Is there a significant association between the level of peer pressure influence and the mental well-being of the participants?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research study employed a correlational research design using a quantitative questionnaire to determine the Level of Peer Pressure Influence and Mental well-being of Grade Eleven Students of Kabankalan Catholic College, Inc. According to Longe (2020), correlational research is a type of research method that involves observing two (2) variables to establish a statistically corresponding relationship between them. It examines whether an increase or decrease in one (1) variable corresponds to an increase or decrease in another variable. The aim of correlational research is to identify variables that have some sort of relationship to the extent that a change in one creates some change in the other.

Participants of the Study

The participants of the study were the grade eleven students of Kabankalan Catholic College, Inc. enrolled in the S.Y. 2023-2024. A total of 223 senior high school students were randomly selected to participate. Specifically, participants were selected from the following academic strands: Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM), Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM), and Technical – Vocational – Livelihood (TVL). The breakdown of the distribution of the respondents is presented below:

Academic Strands	Population	Sample
Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS)	168	71
Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM)	266	112
Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM)	92	38
CSS - Technical Vocational Livelihood	4	2
Total	530	223

Research Instruments

The Perceived Peer Pressure Scale (PPPS)

Developed by Palani and Mani (2016), the initial draft of a 50-item tool assessing perceived peer pressure among higher secondary students underwent scrutiny by experts from the departments of Psychology, Education, and Language. The evaluation focused on content relevance, simplicity, avoidance of repetition, clarity, and appropriateness. Following expert opinions, 30 items were selected and refined, forming a Likert-type Scale with five response options: “Strongly Agree,” “Agree,” “Neutral,” “Disagree,” and “Strongly Disagree.” Given the positively framed nature of all items, scoring was assigned as follows: five (5) for “Strongly Agree,” four (4) for “Agree,” three (3) for “Neutral,” two (2) for “Disagree,” and one (1) for “Strongly Disagree.” Higher scores indicate a heightened perception of peer pressure, while lower scores signify a lower perceived level of peer pressure among higher secondary students.

The Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (WEMWBS)

It is a questionnaire developed by the Universities of Warwick and Edinburgh comprising 14 items that encompass positively formulated statements that capture both emotional and functional dimensions of mental well-being. Respondents express their agreement on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from “none of the time” to “all of the time,” allowing for nuanced responses. The scale is scored by summing the responses to each item, employing a 1 to 5 Likert scale, where higher scores reflect higher levels of mental well-being. The minimum possible scale score is 14, while the maximum is 70. The application of the Warwick–Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale was instrumental in gauging and comprehensively understanding the mental well-being of grade eleven students at Kabankalan Catholic College, Inc.

These instruments collectively provide valuable data to analyze the relationship between perceived peer pressure and mental well-being among the targeted group of students. The Likert scale responses allow for a quantitative evaluation of the student’s perceptions and mental states. The use of established scales, such as the Perceived

Peer Pressure Scale and WEMWBS, enhances the reliability and validity of the research findings.

Bhattacharyya et al.'s study, "A Correlational Analysis of the Relationship between Perceived Peer Pressure and Decision Making in Adolescents," employed the Perceived Peer Pressure Scale (PPPS) questionnaire (2020). The reliability of the study is tested using the Cronbach alpha test ($\alpha = 0.942$). According to Palani and Mani (2016), the tool was a helpful resource for figuring out how peer pressure affected senior high school pupils.

High levels of internal consistency and reliability are demonstrated by the Warwick Edinburgh Mental Well-Being Scale (WEMWBS) in comparison to recognized standards. It is brief, acceptable, and significant to broad demographic groups. It is also reasonably immune to bias and can differentiate between various demographic groups in a manner that is consistent with other population surveys. Support for the single-factor hypothesis came from confirmatory factor analysis. According to Tennant et al. (2007), a Cronbach's alpha score of 0.89 for the student sample and 0.91 for the general sample indicates that the scale has some redundant items.

Data Gathering Procedures

This research study followed a systematic approach to ensure data integrity and reliability. Formal approval letters were secured from relevant offices to protect participants' rights and comply with legal requirements. After approval, printed questionnaires and informed consent forms were distributed to participants, ensuring relevance and reliability. Participants were provided with detailed instructions to ensure a clear survey process. Each completed form marked the end of the initial phase of data collection.

Following the collection of questionnaires, a meticulous organization process and thorough review ensued to ensure adequate answers to all questions. This was crucial for identifying missing or incomplete data and preparing the information for tabulation and analysis.

The data was summarized through tabulation, setting the stage for statistical analysis using various quantitative methods. The results were compiled and presented coherently, making them accessible and understandable to both researchers and evaluators. The compiled findings were forwarded to the Guidance and Testing Office, potentially serving as a foundation for the development of a proposed guidance program.

Data Analysis

This study used statistical tools to analyze data on peer pressure influence and mental well-being among Grade Eleven students at Kabankalan Catholic College, Inc. The mean was used to determine the level of influence and mental well-being based on sex and academic strands. A T-test was used to compare differences based on sex, while an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was applied to compare differences across academic

strands. The Pearson Correlation coefficient was used to analyze the strength and direction of the relationship between these variables. The Pearson Correlation coefficient (r) is the most commonly used metric for determining a linear relationship. It is a number ranging from -1 to 1 that indicates the strength and direction of a link between two variables (Turney, 2023).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1.1 *Level of Peer Pressure in terms of Factor 1: Yielding to Peer Pressure*

No.	Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
4.	I am coerced by my friends to go out with them during weekends	2.93	1.00	Moderate
5.	I have lied many times at the instigation of my friends.	2.70	1.01	Moderate
6.	I have to read some unwanted books due to the compulsion of my friends.	2.62	1.07	Moderate
7.	I am afraid that I will be left alone if I am not a part of whatever my friends do	3.01	1.31	Moderate
8.	I indulge in undesirable activities to satisfy my friends	2.57	1.18	Low
9.	I have to get along with my friend's decisions, whatever it may be	2.73	1.09	Moderate
15.	I would like to have an iPod because my friends expect me to have one	1.94	1.10	Low
27.	I often skip my classes as my friends force me to do so	2.01	1.29	Low
28.	When others make fun of my friends, I ought to defend my friends.	3.68	1.20	High
29.	I have to accept new friends at the urge of my other friends.	3.03	1.05	Moderate
30.	My hairstyle and clothing are according to the wishes of my friends.	2.18	1.24	Low
Total		2.67	.58	Moderate

Legend: 1:00-1.80 (Very Low), 1.81-2.60 (Low), 2.61-3.40 (Moderate), 3.41-4.20 (High), 4.21-5.00 (Very High)

Table 1.1 presents the level of peer pressure in terms of yielding to peer influence among Grade Eleven students at Kabankalan Catholic College, Inc. The data indicates that yielding to peer pressure is a moderate factor ($M=2.67$) among these students, suggesting that they tend to accept their peers' reasonable and non-excessive decisions or persuasive arguments. This is particularly evident in items 8, 15, 27, and 30, which recorded the lowest means of 1.18, 1.10, 1.29, and 1.24, respectively.

These findings were consistent with Lou's (2023) study, "Research on the Influence of Peer Pressure on Adolescents," which highlighted that peer influence can significantly affect adolescents' engagement in risky behaviors, depending on the quality of their friendships. Additionally, item 28, "When others make fun of my friends, I ought to defend my friends," with a mean of 3.68, demonstrates that Grade-Eleven students are inclined to yield to the pressure of defending their friends when confronted with bullying.

This behavior is further supported by Shaheen et al. (2019), which found that adolescents aged 14-16 received the highest levels of social support. Overall, these results imply that the Grade Eleven students of Kabankalan Catholic College, Inc., are less likely to engage in misconduct at the urging of their peers and are more inclined to support their friends, especially in situations involving social issues like bullying.

Table 1.2 Level of Peer Pressure in terms of Factor 2: Resistance to Peer Pressure

No	Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
3.	I am honest with my parents about my whereabouts despite of my friends' objections	3.50	1.06	High
10.	I do not want to have a Facebook account in spite of my friends' compulsion	2.43	1.10	Low
11.	I will not feel bad, if my friends have something that I do not have.	3.62	1.28	High
12.	I like to choose a career of my own, irrespective of my friends' advice.	3.69	1.14	High
13.	I take important decisions without being influenced by my friends' suggestions	3.63	1.12	High
14.	I will enroll myself in Sports and other social service activities even if my friends don't enroll themselves	3.43	1.25	High
16.	I am not crazy with my friends' choices	3.09	1.11	Moderate
17.	I will not fight for unjust causes like my friends	3.27	1.13	Moderate
19.	I stay away, when my friends destroy others properties.	3.42	1.24	High
20.	I do not allow my friends to copy from my home assignments and test related activities.	2.93	1.05	Moderate
21.	I will not go for movies which I do not like even if my friends compel me.	3.07	1.04	Moderate
24.	I like to spend my weekends usefully with my parents and relatives, in spite of my friends' weekend programmes.	3.64	1.13	High
18.	I will not do things against my conscious in spite of my friends' compulsion	3.68	1.20	High
Overall		3.34	.59	Moderate

Legend: 1:00-1.80 (Very Low), 1.81-2.60 (Low), 2.61-3.40 (Moderate), 3.41-4.20 (High), 4.21-5.00 (Very High)

Table 1.2 depicts the level of peer pressure in relation to resistance among Grade-Eleven students at Kabankalan Catholic College, Inc. The data indicated that resistance to peer pressure is a moderate factor (M=3.34) among these students, suggesting that while they are occasionally influenced by their peers, they generally maintain the ability to make independent decisions. This finding aligns with Forney and Ward's (2019) study, which found that peer antisocial behavior significantly influences delinquency and that such behavior negatively impacts a student's ability to resist peer influence. In other words, a student who succumbs to peer pressure in engaging in misconduct may find it increasingly difficult to resist similar influences in the future.

In detail, in the lower category, item 10, "I do not want to have a Facebook account in spite of my friends' compulsion," has a mean of 2.43. This suggested that students are generally resistant to creating a Facebook account even under peer pressure. However, Omoye's (2023) study contrasted this finding, revealing that social media platforms like Facebook and WhatsApp are significant sources of peer pressure, with many young people yielding to such pressure due to a fear of rejection.

Overall, these results implies that Grade Eleven students at Kabankalan Catholic College, Inc., are not overly susceptible to peer influence and demonstrate a strong sense of independence and autonomy. They tend to trust their judgment and values, resisting external pressures. Additionally, they prioritize their family relationships, valuing the support and connection they receive from their families more than the influence of their peers.

Table 1.3 *Level of Peer Pressure in terms of Factor 3: Peer Encouragement*

No	Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1.	Like my friends, I would like to go abroad for higher studies and a job	3.68	1.14	High
2.	I listen to good music as my friends recommend them.	3.67	1.03	High
22.	I get so much encouragement from my friends to solve difficult issues	3.54	1.09	High
23.	I complete my assignments on time at the instance of my friends.	3.28	1.06	Moderate
25.	I joined swimming and other lifesaving training programmes, because of my friends' encouragement	3.09	1.13	Moderate
26.	I get more interest in my studies when my friends motivate me.	3.67	1.18	High
	Overall	3.49	.66	High

Legend: 1.00-1.80 (Very Low), 1.81-2.60 (Low), 2.61-3.40 (Moderate), 3.41-4.20 (High), 4.21-5.00 (Very High)

The table shows the level of peer pressure about peer encouragement. The table reveals that peer encouragement is a significant (M=3.49) predictor of peer pressure among grade eleven students. It demonstrates that peer encouragement and support play a significant role in reinforcing positive behaviors and aspirations in students. Item

number 25 “I joined swimming and other lifesaving training programs, because of my friends’ encouragement” has the lowest mean of 3.09, indicating that there are limited lifesaving training programs accessible, resulting in moderate outcomes.

On the contrary, item number 1 “Like my friends, I would like to go abroad for higher studies and a job” has the highest mean of 3.68. This suggested that participants have a strong social inclination shaped by peers, the advantages of studying and working overseas and possible areas for development in the local job and education systems. This understanding can direct venture plans and, educational programs to meet the needs and aspirations of individuals seeking opportunities abroad. In the study of Sisavath (2021), results revealed that participants benefited from participating in overseas exchanges at a high level in terms of the development of employability skills, particularly interpersonal and communication skills, and multidisciplinary knowledge and international competencies. Study abroad experience was positively considered as being related to increasing job opportunities, which signals better educational credentials with proven skills.

This implies that peer affiliations are deemed important to grade eleven students of Kabankalan Catholic College, Inc. Peer pressure encourages and positively reinforces the responders to set and achieve objectives, make healthy decisions, and participate in constructive activities.

Table 1.4 *Level of Peer Pressure as a Whole*

Subscale	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Factor 1: Yielding to Peer Pressure	2.67	.58	Moderate
Factor 2: Resistance to Peer Pressure	3.34	.59	Moderate
Factor 3: Peer Encouragement	3.49	.66	High
As a whole	3.12	.38	Moderate

Legend: 1.00-1.80 (Very Low), 1.81-2.60 (Low), 2.61-3.40 (Moderate), 3.41-4.20 (High), 4.21-5.00 (Very High)

Table 1.4 presents the overall level of peer pressure influence among Grade Eleven students, encompassing three (3) key factors: Yielding to Peer Pressure, Resistance to Peer Pressure, and Peer Encouragement. The results indicated the mean and standard deviation for each factor: Yielding to Peer Pressure (M=2.67; SD=.58), Resistance to Peer Pressure (M=3.34; SD=.59), Peer Encouragement (M=3.49; SD=.66), and overall Level of Peer Pressure Influence (M=3.12; SD=.38).

The data revealed that Peer Encouragement has the highest mean (M=3.49), categorizing it as a high factor, while Yielding to Peer Pressure has the lowest mean (M=2.67), indicating a moderate influence. Overall, the subscales suggested that peer pressure influence among students is moderate.

These findings aligned with the study by Richard et al. (2022), which showed that peer support is associated with improved mental health, including increased happiness,

self-esteem, and effective coping, as well as lower levels of sadness, loneliness, and anxiety. This positive effect was observed across various groups, including university students, non-student young adults, and ethnic/sexual minorities. Both individual and group peer support are beneficial for mental health, with positive effects extending to those who provide support.

In conclusion, the results suggested that students experience peer pressure influence in multiple dimensions, with varying levels of impact depending on the form of peer interaction.

Table 2 *Level of Mental Well-being of the Participants*

No	Indicators	Mean	SD
1.	I have been feeling optimistic about the future	3.55	.95
2.	I have been feeling useful	3.23	1.00
3.	I have been feeling relaxed	3.04	1.14
4.	I have been feeling interested in other people	3.20	1.16
5.	I have had the energy to spare	3.18	1.05
6.	I have been dealing with problems well	3.21	1.15
7.	I have been thinking clearly	3.25	1.04
8.	I have been feeling good about myself	3.35	1.14
9.	I have been feeling close to other people	3.17	1.10
10.	I have been feeling confident	3.14	1.18
11.	I have been able to make up my mind about things	3.52	1.13
12.	I have been feeling loved	3.57	1.30
13.	I have been feeling interested in new things	3.79	1.18
14.	I have been feeling cheerful	3.48	1.17
Overall		46.70	9.32
Interpretation		Moderate Well-Being	

Legend: *less than 43 (Low Well-being), 43-60 (Moderate Well-being), 60 and above (High Well-being).*

Table 2 presents the results of The Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (WEMWBS) and the corresponding levels of mental well-being among the participants. The WEMWBS yielded a score of 46.70, which is interpreted as “Moderate Well-Being.” Notably, item 13 has the highest mean score of 3.79, suggesting that participants are generally open to exploring new experiences, whether or not they are influenced by their peers. In contrast, item 3 recorded the lowest mean score of 3.04, indicating that respondents, on average, feel less relaxed than they are interested in new activities. This may suggest that the participants are experiencing higher levels of stress or tension, potentially due to academic demands or peer pressure.

Overall, the results implies that while the participants may occasionally experience periods of tension, anxiety, or depression, they are generally managing their daily lives effectively.

Table 3.1 *Difference Analysis on the level of peer pressure influence on the participants when grouped according to Sex*

Factors	Mean	t	p	Conclusion
Factor 1: Yielding to Peer Pressure	M=2.76; F=2.61	1.837	.067	Not Sig.
Factor 2: Resistance to Peer Pressure	M=3.19; F=3.44	-3.005	.003	Highly Sig.
Factor 3: Peer Encouragement	M=3.43; F=3.53	-1.060	.290	Not Sig.
As a whole	M=3.08; F=3.15	-1.374	.172	Not Sig.

Legend: M-Male, F-Female; Not Sig. if p-value is greater than 0.05; sig. and highly sig. if p-value is less than 0.05 and 0.01, respectively.

Table 3 shows the difference analysis on the level of peer pressure influence when grouped according to sex (Male = 3.08; Female = 3.15, p-value .172) which is interpreted as not significant as a whole. However, Factor 2: Resistance to Peer Pressure with a p-value of .003 reveals a significance alpha level of 0.05 which is highly significant.

The findings indicated that women are more likely than men to encounter peer pressure, indicating that gender variations or differences exist in various manners that peer pressure affects both sexes.

On the contrary, the study of Xiong and Vang (2023) revealed that boys are more likely to engage in risky behaviors and be pressured, but there is no gender difference in resisting peer influence. Females are more likely to stand up for their beliefs than conform to their peers.

Table 3.2 *Difference Analysis on the Level of Peer Pressure Influence on the Participants when grouped according to Strand*

Factors	Mean	F	p	Conclusion
Factor 1: Yielding to Peer Pressure	H=2.77; S=2.64 A=2.63; T=2.19	1.332	.265	Not Sig.
Factor 2: Resistance to Peer Pressure	H=3.16; S=3.45 A=3.38; T=2.26	6.090	.001	Highly Sig.
Factor 3: Peer Encouragement	H=3.27; S=3.62 A=3.56; T=2.42	6.205	.000	Highly Sig.
As a whole	H=3.04; S=3.19 A=3.14; T=2.27	5.878	.001	Highly Sig.

Legend: H=HUMSS, S=STEM, A=ABM, T=TVL; Not Sig. if p-value is greater than 0.05; sig. and highly sig. if p-value is less than 0.05 and 0.01, respectively.

Table 3.2 presents an analysis of the differences in peer pressure influence across four academic strands: Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM), Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM), and Technical, Vocational, and Livelihood Studies (CSS). The data showed that STEM students have the highest mean score of 3.19, indicating a greater level of peer pressure influence, while students in CSS - Technical, Vocational, and Livelihood have the lowest mean score of 2.27.

The results suggested that STEM students at Kabankalan Catholic College, Inc., experience a higher level of peer pressure compared to students in other strands. This

finding aligned with Fragata and Limpot's (2023) research, which highlighted the significant impact of peer pressure on the academic performance of STEM students in the Philippines. Their study underscored the considerable effect peer pressure has on students' task completion effectiveness.

A one-way repeated measures ANOVA was conducted to assess whether there are significant differences in peer pressure influence among the different academic strands. The analysis revealed a p-value of 0.001, which is below the alpha level of 0.05, indicating a highly significant difference in peer pressure influence across the strands.

Table 4.1 *Difference Analysis on the mental well-being on the participants when grouped according to Sex*

Variable	Mean	t	p	Conclusion
Mental Well-Being	M=48.50; F=45.48	2.399	.017	Sig.

Legend: M=Male, F=Female; Not Sig. if p-value is greater than 0.05; sig. and highly sig. if p-value is less than 0.05 and 0.01, respectively.

Table 4 shows the difference analysis on the level of mental well-being when grouped according to sex (Male=48.50; Female=45.48). The presented data indicated that men possess higher mental well-being in comparison to women. Similarly, the results indicated that women are more likely than men to experience emotional and mental challenges. Women were found to be more likely to suffer from emotional problems and depression than men under the influence of biological basis, general psychological characteristics, and social environment interference (Tang & Zhang, 2022).

Whilst the levels of mental and physical well-being of men and women differed, the data nevertheless showed that both sexes had a substantial degree of well-being, indicating that both sexes represent a considerable level of mental well-being.

The results of the study obtained, (t=2.399, p=.017) a p-value which is lesser than the alpha level of significance, 0.05. Thus, it indicated that the results of the data on the participants' mental well-being when categorized by sex are significant, indicating that the participants' mental well-being varies depending on their sex.

Table 4.2 *Difference Analysis on the mental well-being on the participants when grouped according to Strand*

Variable	Mean	F	p	Conclusion
Mental Well-Being	H=46.17; S=48.18 A=44.29; T=28.50	4.624	.004	Highly Sig.

Legend: H=HUMSS, S=STEM, A=ABM, T=TVL; Not Sig. if p-value is greater than 0.05; sig. and highly sig. if p-value is less than 0.05 and 0.01, respectively.

Table 4.2 presents an analysis of the differences in mental well-being among participants when grouped by academic strand. The mean scores for each strand are as follows: STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) has a mean of

48.18; ABM (Accountancy, Business, and Management) has a mean of 44.29; Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) has a mean of 46.17; and CSS (Technical, Vocational, and Livelihood) has a mean of 28.50. The data indicated that CSS has the lowest mean score at 28.50, while STEM has the highest mean score at 48.18. This suggests that STEM students exhibit the highest level of mental well-being compared to students in other strands.

The correlation analysis, as shown in the table, revealed a p-value of 0.004, indicating a highly significant association between the level of mental well-being and the academic strand. Since this p-value is less than the significance level of 0.05, there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

These results implies that Grade Eleven students with higher mental well-being are more likely to be in the STEM strand. However, this does not mean that all academic strands reflect the same level of mental well-being uniformly. Instead, the data highlighted a strong correlation between students' mental well-being and their academic strand classification.

Table 5 *Correlation Analysis on the level of peer pressure influence and mental well-being of the participants*

Variables	r	p	Conclusion
Yielding to Peer Pressure*Mental-Well Being	.040	.557	Not Sig.
Resistance to Peer Pressure*Mental-Well Being	.282	.000	Highly Sig.
Peer Encouragement*Mental-Well Being	.236	.000	Highly Sig.
Peer Pressure Influence*Mental-Well Being	.294	.000	Highly Sig.

Not Sig. if p-value is greater than 0.05; sig. and highly sig. if p-value is less than 0.05 and 0.01, respectively.

Table 5 presents the r-computed values for the relationship between peer pressure factors and mental well-being: Yielding to Peer Pressure and Mental Well-Being ($r = 0.040$), Resistance to Peer Pressure and Mental Well-Being ($r = 0.282$), Peer Encouragement and Mental Well-Being ($r = 0.236$), and Peer Pressure Influence on Mental Well-Being ($r = 0.294$). Among these, only the correlation for Yielding to Peer Pressure is not statistically significant ($p\text{-value} = 0.557$), whereas the correlations for Resistance to Peer Pressure and Peer Encouragement are significant, with $p\text{-values}$ lower than the alpha level of 0.05 ($p = 0.000$), indicating high significance.

Linear regression analysis revealed that Resistance to Peer Pressure and Peer Encouragement were the most significant factors associated with mental well-being, showing the strongest predictive power for participants' mental health. This finding is consistent with Cruz et al.'s (2022) study, which noted that respondents exhibited low levels of yielding to peer pressure, high levels of resistance to peer pressure, and high levels of peer encouragement, although they also had low levels of mental well-being. The study concluded a significant correlation between peer pressure and mental well-being.

The results indicated a strong correlation between peer pressure and mental well-being among Grade Eleven students at Kabankalan Catholic College, Inc. This association is directional, meaning that an increase in one variable tends to correspond with an increase or decrease in the other. Specifically, students who are more psychologically healthy tend to experience less peer pressure, while those who are more socially confident and well-mannered often face more peer pressure.

Supporting this, Montes (2019) found a positive moderate correlation between social influence and mental health among senior high school students, suggesting that the level of social influence can significantly affect mental health.

Overall, the p-value reported ($p = 0.001$) is below the 0.05 alpha level of significance, confirming the study's rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicated a significant relationship between peer pressure influence and mental well-being among Grade Eleven students at Kabankalan Catholic College, Inc.

Conclusions

The study aimed to evaluate the levels of peer pressure influence and mental well-being among Grade Eleven students at Kabankalan Catholic College, Inc. for the Academic Year 2023-2024. The findings revealed that peer pressure is influenced by three (3) key factors: yielding to peer pressure, resistance to peer pressure, and peer encouragement, with each factor showing a moderate level of influence. Students experienced varying degrees of peer pressure, with some encountering high levels and others lower levels. The study found that participants generally managed their mental well-being effectively, maintaining a moderate level of psychological health.

When analysed by sex and academic strand, the data indicated no significant difference between male and female students regarding peer pressure influence, although resistance to peer pressure was notably significant. Among the academic strands, students in the STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) category showed the highest mean of peer pressure influence, while those in the CSS (Technical, Vocational, and Livelihood) category had the lowest mean. This suggests that peer pressure impacts STEM students more significantly than those in other strands.

In terms of mental well-being, the results varied by sex and academic strand, with both genders demonstrating significant well-being levels. The study found a substantial correlation between mental well-being and strand-based categorization, indicating that students in different strands experience varying levels of mental well-being. The analysis also revealed a strong association between peer pressure and mental well-being, with significant statistical support ($p\text{-value} = 0.001$), leading to the rejection of the null

hypothesis. This result confirms a meaningful link between peer pressure influence and mental well-being.

Recommendations

Based on these findings, several recommendations are proposed.

Students should be encouraged to express their concerns about peer pressure and understand its potential impact on their mental health.

Parents can benefit from increased awareness of how peer pressure affects their children, enabling them to implement effective support measures.

Teachers should develop a deeper understanding of student behaviors related to peer pressure and tailor their interventions accordingly. The institution's Counselling and Testing Office should continue to create and promote programs that address peer pressure and support mental well-being.

Finally, this study could serve as a foundation for future researchers interested in analysing the numerous aspects influencing peer pressure and mental well-being, given they have an enthusiasm in this particular field.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The institution's Research Internal Ethics Committee approved the research study before the survey was released, guaranteeing that all relevant ethical factors were taken into account. Through the use of a thorough permission form that detailed the goals, methods, and rights of the study, all participants gave their informed consent, attesting to their voluntary participation and their freedom to discontinue participation at any moment without incurring any fees. By acknowledging the autonomy and dignity of every participant and granting them the freedom to renounce participation at any time, respect for persons was maintained. Beneficence and non-maleficence were given top priority in order to protect participants and avoid any harm. Moreover, by safeguarding personal information and anonymity responses, participants' identities were kept safe and confidentiality and anonymity were rigorously upheld. The researchers made sure that every participant's rights, privacy, and welfare were upheld during the study by following these ethical guidelines.

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